

NEW MODEL OF UNIVERSE DARK ENERGY EXPLAINED

The current model of the universe is based on Big Bang theory. According to Big Bang theory, our universe is expanding continuously. Experimentally we also observed expanding the universe. The expanding speed increases with time and distance. This is known as dark energy.

But still, now we would not be able to find the source of dark energy which is a great drawback of the standard model.

To explain the source of dark energy Mr Somnath Chakraborty considers a new model of the universe which is published in October issues of 'IJNRD' in volume 3.

You can read the paper by scanning this QR code (left) or go through this link: [<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1477252>].

According to this model, Universe is finite of the order of 10^{15} m. The universe has a massive centre. The total mass of all other objects is negligible compared to the mass of that centre.

New model of universe is given in the figure below...

Region A is the unsafe region because all objects within this region feel great attraction force by a massive centre. Due to this great attraction force, all objects within this region feel accelerating force towards the centre and the objects are accelerate along the centre.

Now, we consider three points D, E and F within the unsafe region. Let us consider that the Milky Way is at point E. Now the objects at D are more close to the massive centre compare to E . so, the velocity of objects at D must be greater than the objects at E. so, for an observer from E, D must go far away .i.e the observer fell universe is expanding.

On the other hand, the velocity E is greater than the velocity of F. so, the distance between E and F increases with time. So, according to an observer at E, objects at F go far away from him. So, overall all objects go far away from the observer at E. this is observed practically. So, from this model of the universe, dark energy is nothing but the great gravitational pull due to the massive centre of our universe.

Due to the limitation of instruments, we are able to see very negligible part of our universe. For this limitation of instruments, we are in the wrong concept that our universe is expanding. If we consider the vastness of the universe and the new model of the universe, then actually universe contracts towards the massive centre of the universe. Due to the contraction, the distance of objects in an unsafe region from the massive centre decreases with time. For this reason, the amount of red-shift for distance object increases with time and distance.

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